

LIBERATION OF IODINE BY "FORMAMIDINE DISULPHIDE" SALTS. CONSTITUTION OF 'FORMAMIDINE DISULPHIDE SALTS'

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Influence of dilution, concentration of KI, addition of acids and thiocarbamide, and the dielectric constant of the medium on the change of thiol \rightleftharpoons disulphide have been investigated by titrating the amount of iodine set free and the acid formed.

Reynolds and Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 1) found that within certain limits thiocarbamide, like mercaptans, could be titrated directly with iodine (cf. Klason and Carlson, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 738; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 119; Sampey and Reid, *ibid.*, 1932, 54, 3404). Thus,

"Formamidine disulphide" salt.

The reversible nature of the above reaction, however, was recognised first by Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2166). According to him, the liberation of iodine, under certain conditions from alkali iodide, by "formamidine disulphide" salts (since the free base is not known) is due to the reverse reaction of the above change, the acid (or anion) forming salt with the base having no primary function in this regard. Since (i) reversibility in the true physico-chemical sense, as distinct from more or less ease of oxidation and reduction, in the process Thiol \rightleftharpoons Disulphide, generally, is doubtful and a subject of controversy (*Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1949, 18, 27, 28; Michaelis, "Physical Methods of Organic Chemistry", Vol. II. Ed. by Weissberger, 1946, p. 1109; Preisler and Berger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 322), and (ii) results throwing doubt on the disulphide structure of "formamidine disulphide" have been already reported (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 119, 309, 341), a re-examination of the above system appeared warranted. Experiments were therefore undertaken to investigate the influence of dilution, potassium iodide concentration, addition of acids and thiocarbamide, and of dielectric constant of the medium, on the above change; in each case the quantity of iodine set free and acid formed were measured. For comparison similar observations were taken with "tetramethylformamidine disulphide" hydrobromide (Lecher, *Annalen*, 1925, 445, 36, 51; Sahasrabudhey, *loc. cit.*) and those with respect to dilution and potassium iodide concentration are reported. The results are presented in Tables I to VIII and Fig. 1.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Influence of Dilution.—"Formamidine disulphide" hydrobromide (1.4 g.) was dissolved to give 20 c. c. solution and 2 c. c. of this were diluted with varying quantities of water and treated with a fixed quantity (2 c. c.) of 20% potassium

iodide solution. Iodine was at once liberated, which was determined titrimetrically with a *N*/10 thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator. This was followed by an estimation of the acidity of the solution with *N*/10-sodium hydroxide. The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

The hydrobromide soln. taken = 2 c. c.

Expt. No.	Dilution.	KI.	<i>N</i> /10- Thio.	<i>N</i> /10-Alkali.	Total thio+alkali.
1	—	—	—	9.0 c.c.	9.0 c.c.
2	—	(Excess of solid KI)	8.5 c.c.	0.5	9.0
3	—	2 c.c.	4.1	4.9	9.0
4	10 c.c.	„	3.95	5.0	8.95
5	25	„	3.7	5.3	9.0
6	100	„	2.8	5.85	8.65
7	200	„	1.0	7.95	8.95
8	400	„	0.25	8.65	8.96

Influence of Potassium Iodide Concentration.—“Formamidine disulphide” hydrobromide (1.56 g.) was dissolved to give 20 c. c. solution and to a fixed volume of it varying quantities of a strong potassium iodide solution (50%) were added and the bulk of the mixture made up to a fixed volume. Iodine and acid liberated were determined. The results are presented in Table II.

TABLE II

Hydrobromide soln.—2 c. c. Bulk of the mix.—11.0 c. c.

Expt. No.	KI.	H ₂ O added.	Thio.	<i>N</i> /10- Alkali	Alkali+thio.
1	5.0 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	4.50 c.c.	5.4 c.c.	9.90 c.c.
2	2.5	7.5	3.85	6.0	9.85
3	1.25	8.75	3.55	6.3	9.85
4	0.60	9.4	3.20	6.6	9.80
5	0.30	9.7	2.65	7.2	9.85

Influence of the added Acid.—“Formamidine disulphide” hydrobromide (0.79 g.) was dissolved to give 20 c. c. solution, 2 c. c. of which were treated with varying volumes of 5*N* sulphuric acid and a fixed quantity of potassium iodide. In each case the final bulk of the mixture was made up to 20 c. c. with water and the liberated iodine estimated. The results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III

Hydrobromide soln.—2.0 c. c. Vol. of the mixture—20 c. c. 50% KI—5 c. c.

Expt. No.	...	1	2	3	4	5	6
5 <i>N</i> -H ₂ SO ₄ added (c.c.)	...	1.0	3.0	5.0	7.0	10.0	12.0
<i>N</i> /10-Thio (c.c.)	...	3.0	3.1	3.3	3.35	3.5	3.7

Influence of addition of Thiocarbamide.—The hydrobromide (0.62 g) was dissolved to give 20 c. c. solution. The thiocarbamide solution contained 1.57 g. in 50 c. c. The results are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Hydrobromide soln.—2.0 c. c. Vol. of the mixture—20 c. c.

Expt. No.	Thiocarbamide.	50% KI.	<i>N</i> /10- Thio.	<i>N</i> /10-alkali.	Thio + alkali.
1	2.0 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	27 c.c.	1.1 c.c.	3.8 c.c.
2	5.0	"	2.3	1.6	3.9
3	7.0	"	2.2	1.6	3.8
4	10.0	"	2.1	1.8	3.9
5	12.0	"	1.9	1.9	3.8

Influence of addition of Hydriodic Acid.—The hydrobromide (1.5 g.) was dissolved to give 20 c. c. solution. Experiments were carried out along the same lines as in Table II, a strong solution of hydriodic acid being used instead of potassium iodide. The results are presented in Table V.

TABLE V

Hydrobromide soln.—2.0 c. c.

Expt. No.	*HI added.	Water added.	<i>N</i> /10- Thio.	<i>N</i> /10- Alkali.	Thio + alkali.
1	—	—	—	9.6 c.c.	9.6 c.c.
2	(Solid KI)	—	9.4 c.c.	0.0	9.4
3	*1.0 c.c.	1.0	4.3	**20.65 (5.0)***	9.3
4	"	100	2.6	22.50 (6.85)	9.45
5	2.0	—	5.0	35.60 (4.30)	9.30
6	4.0	—	6.0	65.40 (2.80)	8.8

* 1 c. c. of HI=0.1987 g. iodine=0.26 g. KI=1.565 c. c. *N*/10-alkali.

** These figures represent the direct titre value.

*** These figures (bracketed) represent the quantity of alkali required for the acid formed from the hydrobromide and have been obtained by subtracting the corresponding HI equivalent (calculated from column 2) from the titre value directly obtained (column 5).

Similar experiments with respect to the influence of dilution and potassium iodide concentration were carried out with the hydrobromide of tetramethylformamide disulphide (Sahasrabudhey, *loc. cit.*). The results are presented in Tables VI and VII which are self explanatory (cf. Tables I and II).

Tetramethylformamide disulphide hydrobromide (0.955 g.) was dissolved to give 50 c. c. solution.*

TABLE VI

Influence of dilution.

Hydrobromide soln. = 5.0 c. c.					
Expt. No.	KI (20%).	Dilution.	N/10- Thio.	N/10- Alkali.	Thio + alkali.
1	5.0 c.c.	25 c.c.	3.0 c.c.	1.3 c.c.	4.3 c.c.
2	"	50	2.7	1.7	4.4
3	"	100	2.3	2.05	4.35
4	"	200	1.6	2.8	4.4
5	"	400	0.8	3.7	4.5
6	"	—	4.1	0.3	4.4
7	"	—	—	4.5	4.5

Influence of Potassium Iodide Concentration.—The tetramethylformamide disulphide hydrobromide (1.91g) was dissolved to give 50 c. c. solution, 5.0 c.c. of which were used in the experiments in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Vol. of the mixture = 25 c. c.

Expt. No.	KI (20%).	Water added.	N/10-Thio.	N/10- Alkali.	Alkali + thio.
1	10.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	5.9	2.7 c.c.	8.6 c.c.
2	5.0	15.0	5.7	2.9	8.6
3	2.5	17.5	5.5	3.1	8.6
4	1.25	18.75	4.95	3.7	8.65
5	0.62	19.4	3.5	5.2	8.7
6	0.31	19.7	2.0	6.9	8.9
7	—	25.0	—	9.0	9.0

*Influence of the Dielectric Constant of the Medium.***—Formamide disulphide hydriodide (2.03 g., prepared according to Werner's procedure, *loc. cit.*) was dissolved to

It is not possible to carry out these experiments with about $M/2$ solutions as in the case of "formamide disulphide" hydrobromide (vide Table I). Approximately $M/10$ solution was therefore used.

** cf. Werner, *J. loc. cit.*

give 20 c. c. solution, 1 c. c. of which was added to a fixed weight of the solvent (alcohol-water mixtures so prepared as to give a wide range of dielectric constants), and the iodine set free estimated colorimetrically as well as titrimetrically with thiosulphate. The results are summarised in Table VIII (Fig. 1).

TABLE VIII

Wt. of the mixture—20 g.

Expt. No.	% Absolute alcohol in mix. by wt.	D^* at 40°.	Bulk of the mixture.	Iodine set free in terms of $N/10$ thio.	Iodine colorimetrically determined. $N/10-I_2$ (in 20 c.c. bulk).
1	8	70	20.4 c.c.	<0.05 c.c.	Imperceptible
2	16	66	20.8	0.05	Do
3	24	60	21.2	0.10	<0.05 c.c.
4	32	55.5	21.6	0.20	0.05
5	40	51	22.0	0.40	0.10
6	50	45	22.5	0.60	0.15
7	60	39	23.0	0.70	0.25
8	75	32	23.8	0.80	0.40
9	85	27.5	24.2	1.00	0.70
10	100	22.5	25.0	1.80	0.90

* Dielectric constant data as per Landolt & Börnstein & others. *Physikalische-Chemische* Table III, p. 1969 by J. Wyman jr.

DISCUSSION

From the results in Table I to VIII it is evident that the reaction

is a truly reversible system, which shows mobility comparable with an ionic process and is influenced, in addition to the concentration of the reactants and resultants, by dilution and the dielectric constant of the medium. Further, since (i) the quantity of iodine set free by the reverse change and the acid formed, presumably by the decomposition and/or "hydrolysis" of the "salt" show very definite interdependence, their sum total being always constant, (ii) added external acid favours iodine liberation, and (iii) this last is also profoundly influenced by the dielectric constant of the medium, *i. e.* in general, factors which would hinder or suppress

dissociation or hydrolysis of the "salt" favour iodine liberation, the conclusion that 'anion' of the "salt" partakes in this change is patent. In short, the iodine liberating capacity is possessed by the "salt" molecule as a whole (unhydrolysed and undissociated) and is not due to the base only, as suggested earlier (Werner, *loc. cit.*). If Werner's mechanism, namely, decomposition of disulphide link (cf. Fromm, *Annalen*, 1906, 348 144) as a prerequisite of the above reverse change be assumed, the following difficulties arise : (i) "anion" of the "formamidine disulphide salt" will

Fig. 1

not partake in such a process, (ii) the process will constitute essentially a cleavage of the covalent S-S link which from the known facts about this bond cannot be influenced by ionic processes as has been observed in the present case, and (iii) though iodine would be liberated by the neutral free thyl radicals (Lecher, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 524; 1920, 53, 577; Schonberg, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 17), if they are formed, their formation is known only in indifferent solvents and on impartation of thermal energy, both of these factors being inoperative in this case.

Another noteworthy feature of the oxidation of thiocarbamide is that the change: thiocarbamide \rightarrow oxidation product, is known to be reversible only in presence of iodine and the ion I^- , a fact which cannot be explained on the disulphide view of the constitution of the latter. In other reactions where iodine is known to be liberated (by oxidation of HI) by say, the N-haloamides, the conditions applied are vastly different (Whitley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 359), and then the process is not reversible.

On the above considerations it is concluded therefore, that the reversibility of the present process (Preisler and Berger, *loc. cit.*) is not due to the reversible disruption of the disulphide link but arises as a result of certain special properties of the link between electron deficient (positive) molecule ion of thiocarbamide formed by the loss of an electron by oxidation (Weitz, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 2307; Sahasrabudhey, *loc. cit.*, pp. 119, 309) and negative I^- .

which combination (II) is bound to be formed (from any "salt" of the base) to a greater or less extent in presence of iodine ions in an ionising medium by a simple exchange process; thus:

What can be the possible mode of attachment of iodine to the thiocarbamide residue envisaged above is being discussed separately.

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